

EFFICACY OF MODIFIED LIMBERG FLAP SUTURING TECHNIQUES IN THE SURGICAL MANAGEMENT OF CICATRICIAL CONTRACTURES OF THE PLANTAR SURFACE OF THE FOOT

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ABSTRACT

Cicatricial contractures of the plantar surface of the foot represent a significant challenge in reconstructive plastic surgery due to associated functional impairment, pain, and limited mobility. These deformities commonly develop following burns, trauma, or previous surgical interventions and can substantially reduce a patient's quality of life. Among various reconstructive techniques, the Limberg rhomboid flap is widely used due to its versatility, reliability, and robust vascular supply. However, conventional suturing methods may not ensure optimal tension distribution in weight-bearing areas such as the plantar surface. Therefore, modifications of suturing techniques in Limberg flap procedures are of considerable clinical importance.

Introduction

Cicatricial contractures of the plantar surface of the foot represent a significant challenge in reconstructive plastic surgery due to associated functional impairment, pain, and limited mobility. These deformities commonly develop following burns, trauma, or previous surgical interventions and can substantially reduce a patient's quality of life. Among various reconstructive techniques, the Limberg rhomboid flap is widely used due to its versatility, reliability, and robust vascular supply. However, conventional suturing methods may not ensure optimal tension distribution in weight-bearing areas such as the plantar surface. Therefore, modifications of suturing techniques in Limberg flap procedures are of considerable clinical importance.

Aim of the Study

To evaluate the effectiveness of a modified suturing technique in Limberg flap plastic surgery for the treatment of plantar cicatricial contractures.

Materials and Methods

The study included patients with post-burn and post-traumatic cicatricial contractures of the plantar surface of the foot. All patients underwent surgical reconstruction using the Limberg flap technique. In the main group, a modified suturing technique was applied to reduce tension along wound edges and improve flap adaptation, while the control group received conventional suturing.

Clinical outcomes were evaluated based on wound healing time, incidence of postoperative complications (including necrosis, infection, and wound dehiscence), functional

recovery, and patient satisfaction. Follow-up assessments were carried out over a period of 3–6 months.

Results

Comparative analysis demonstrated that the modified suturing technique resulted in improved clinical outcomes compared to the conventional method. The average wound healing time in the main group was shorter (10–14 days) than in the control group (14–18 days), with faster epithelialization and more stable wound closure.

The incidence of postoperative complications, including partial flap necrosis, wound dehiscence, and infection, was lower in the main group. These improvements are likely associated with better vascular preservation and reduced tissue tension. Functional recovery was also enhanced, as patients in the main group regained weight-bearing ability earlier (within 3–4 weeks) compared to those in the control group (4–6 weeks). Recurrence of contractures during the follow-up period was minimal.

Furthermore, scar quality was superior in the main group, demonstrating increased elasticity and improved aesthetic appearance. Overall, the modified suturing technique ensured more reliable healing and better functional outcomes.

Discussion

The findings indicate that optimization of suturing techniques in Limberg flap procedures plays a crucial role in improving surgical outcomes. The plantar surface presents unique biomechanical challenges that require careful management of tension vectors and load distribution. The modified suturing approach enhances flap viability and reduces the risk of contracture recurrence. These results are consistent with previous studies emphasizing the importance of tension-free closure in reconstructive surgery.

Conclusion

The modified Limberg flap suturing technique is an effective and reliable method for the treatment of plantar cicatricial contractures. It promotes faster healing, reduces complications, and improves functional outcomes. This technique can be recommended for broader clinical application in reconstructive plastic surgery.

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